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APPROACHES OF DATAMINING IN NETWORK INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Network security technology has become crucial in protecting government and industry computing infrastructure. Due to the network attacks over the past few years the intrusion detection system (IDS) is increasingly becoming a crucial component to secure network. In recent years, data mining - based intrusion detection systems (IDSs) have demonstrated high accuracy, good generalization to novel types of intrusion, and robust behaviour in a changing environment. . Instrumenting components such as model deployment, data transformations, and cooperative distributed detection remain a labour intensive and complex engineering endeavour. In data mining based intrusion detection system we should have thorough knowledge about the particular domain in relation to intrusion detection so as to efficiently extract relative rule from huge amounts of records. Modern intrusion detection applications face complex requirements - they need to be reliable, extensible, easy to manage, and have low maintenance cost. Still, significant challenges exist in design and implementation of production quality IDSs. This paper gives the classifier algorithm model for attack category and ensemble approach for detection.

KEYWORDS: *Data mining, Ensemble approach, Network intrusion detection system, classifier, network security, Algorithm selection.*

INTRODUCTION

In the era of information society, computer networks and their related applications are becoming more popular network technologies have provided us with new life and shopping experiences, particularly in the fields of e-business, e-learning and e-money. But along with network development, there has come a huge increase in network crime. It not only greatly affects our everyday life, which relies heavily on networks and Internet technologies, but also damages computer systems that serve our daily activities, including business, learning, entertainment and so on. To defend against various cyber -attacks and computer viruses, lots of computer security techniques have been intensively studied in the last decade, namely cryptography, firewalls, anomaly and intrusion detection . Among them, network intrusion detection (NID) has been considered to be one of the most promising methods for defending complex and dynamic intrusion behaviours . Intrusion detection techniques using data mining have attracted more and more interest these years. . Anomaly detection is based on profiles that represent normal behaviour of users, hosts, networks, and detecting attacks of significant deviation from these profiles.

DATA MINING

Data mining (sometimes called data or knowledge discovery) is the process of analyzing data from different perspectives and summarizing it into useful information - information that can be used to increase revenue, cuts costs, or both. It allows users to analyze data from many different dimensions or angles, categorize it, and summarize the relationships identified. Data mining software is one of a number of analytical tools for analyzing data. Technically, data mining is the process of finding correlations or patterns among dozens of fields in large relational databases. Mining can efficiently discover useful and interesting rules from large collection of data. It is a fairly recent topic in computer science but utilizes many older computational techniques from statistics ,information retrieval, machine learning and pattern recognition. Data mining is disciplines works to finds the major relations between collections of data and enables to discover a new and anomalies behavior. Data mining based intrusion detection techniques generally fall into one of two categories; misuse detection and anomaly detection. In misuse detection, each instance in a data set is labeled as 'normal' or 'intrusion' and a learning algorithm is trained over the labeled data. These techniques are able to automatically retrain intrusion detection models on different input data that include new types of attacks, as long as they have been labeled appropriately. Data mining are used in different field such as marketing, financial affairs and business organizations in general and proof it is success. The main approaches of data mining that are used including classification which maps a data item into one of several predefined categories. This approach normally output "classifiers" has ability to classify new data in the future, for example, in the form of decision trees or rules. An ideal application in intrusion detection will be together sufficient "normal" and "abnormal" audit data for a user or a program.

NETWORK INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM

A network-based ID system is a tool that monitors the traffic on its network segment as a data source. Network traffic on other segments, and traffic on other means of communication (like phone lines) can't be monitored. Both network-based and host-based ID sensors have pros and cons. This is generally accomplished by placing the network interface card in promiscuous mode to capture all network traffic that crosses its network segment In the end, you'll probably want a combination of both. Network-based ID involves looking at the packets on the network as they pass by some sensor. The sensor can only see the packets that happen to be carried on the network segment it's attached to. Packets are considered to be of interest if they match a signature. String signatures look for a text string that indicates a possible attack. An example string signature for UNIX might be "cat "+ "+" > /.rhosts" , which if successful, might cause a UNIX system to become extremely vulnerable to network attack. Three primary types of signatures are string signatures, port signatures, and header condition signatures . Header signatures watch for dangerous or illogical combinations in packet headers. To refine the string signature to reduce the number of false positives, it may be necessary to use a compound string signature. A compound string signature for a common Web server attack might be "cgi-bin" AND "a glimpse" AND "IFS". Port signatures simply watch for connection attempts to well-known, frequently attacked ports. Examples of these ports include telnet (TCP port 23), FTP (TCP port 21/20), SUNRPC (TCP/UDP port 111), and IMAP (TCP port 143). If any of these ports aren't used by

the site, then incoming packets to these ports are suspicious. The most famous example is WinNuke, where a packet is destined for a NetBIOS port and the Urgent pointer, or Out Of Band pointer is set. This resulted in the "blue screen of death" for Windows systems. Another well-known header signature is a TCP packet with both the SYN and FIN flags set, signifying that the requestor wishes to start and stop a connection at the same time.

NETWORK SECURITY

Network security involves the authorization of access to data in a network, which is controlled by the network administrator. Networks can be private, such as within a company, and others which might be open to public access. Network security consists of the provisions and policies adopted by a network administrator to prevent and monitor unauthorized access, misuse, modification, or denial of a computer network and network-accessible resources. Network security covers a variety of computer networks, both public and private, that are used in everyday jobs conducting transactions and communications among businesses, government agencies and individuals. Users choose or are assigned an ID and password or other authenticating information that allows them access to information and programs within their authority. Network security is involved in organizations, enterprises, and other types of institutions. It does as its title explains: It secures the network, as well as protecting and overseeing operations being done. The most common and simple way of protecting a network resource is by assigning it a unique name and a corresponding password.

EVALUATION OF ANAMOLY DETECTION

There are generally two types of attacks in network intrusion detection: the attacks that involve single connections and the attacks that involve multiple connections (bursts of connections). The standard metrics in Table 1 treat all types of attacks similarly thus failing to provide sufficiently generic and systematic evaluation for the attacks that involve many network connections. the individual classifications over all classifiers. There are several methods to update the weights and combine the individual classifiers. After the k th decision tree is built, the total misclassification error of the tree, defined as the sum of the weights of misclassified tuples over the sum of the weights of all tuples, is calculated: (2) where i loops over all instances in the data sample. Then, the weights of misclassified tuples are increased (3) Finally, the new weights are renormalized as, and the tree $k+1$ is constructed. Note that, as the algorithm progresses, the predominance of hard-to-classify instances in the training set is increased. The final classification of tuple I is a weighted sum of the classifications over the individual trees. Furthermore, trees with lower misclassification errors " k " are given more weight when the final classification is computed

CLASSIFIER ALGORITHMS

NBTree

NBTree [6] is a hybrid between decision trees and Naïve Bayes. It creates trees whose leaves are Naïve Bayes classifiers for the instances that reach the leaf. It is quite reasonable to expect that NBTree can outperform Naïve Bayes; but instead, we may have to scarify some speed.

Decision Table

Decision Table [7] builds a decision table majority classifier. It evaluates feature subsets using best-first search and can use cross-validation for evaluation. There is a set of methods that can be used in the search phase (E.g.: BestFirst, RankSearch, GeneticSearch ...) and we may also use LBk to assist the result. In this experiment, we choose the crossVal = 1; searchMethod = BestFirst and useLBk = False

BayesNet

BayesNet [4] learns Bayesian networks under the presumptions: nominal attributes (numeric one are predescretized) and no missing values (any such values are replaced globally). There are two different parts for estimating the conditional probability tables of the network. We run Bayes Net with the Simple Estimator and K2 search algorithm without using AD Tree.

Naive Bayes

The Naive Bayes [4] classifier provides a simple approach, with clear semantics, to representing and learning probabilistic knowledge. It is termed naïve because it relies on two important simplifying assumptions that the predictive attributes are conditionally independent given the class, and it posits that no hidden or latent attributes influence the prediction process.

ANAMOLY DETECTION

Anomaly detection techniques can help humans prioritize potentially anomalous records for review. In spite of efforts to update defences, new attacks may slip through defences and be labelled as either normal network traffic, or else filtered as a known but benign probe. Catching new attacks cannot depend on the current set of classification rules. Since classification assumes that incoming data will match that seen in the past, classification may be an inappropriate approach to finding new attacks. Much of the work in outlier detection has been approached from a statistical point of view and is primarily concerned with one or very few attributes. Clustering is an unsupervised machine learning technique for finding patterns in unlabelled data with many dimensions (number of attributes). However, because the network data has many dimensions, we have investigated use of clustering for anomaly detection. We use k-means clustering to find natural groupings of similar alarm records. Records that are far from any of these clusters indicate unusual activity that may be part of a new attack.

CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUES

In a classification task in machine learning, the main task is to take each and every instance of a dataset and assign it to a particular class. A classification based IDS attempts to classify all traffic as either normal or malicious. The challenge in this is to minimize the number of false positives (classification of normal traffic as malicious) and false negatives (classification of malicious traffic as normal). There are five general categories of techniques have been tried to perform classification for intrusion detection purposes:

A. Inductive Rule Generation

The RIPPER System is probably the most popular representative of this classification mechanism. RIPPER [2] is a rule learning program. RIPPER is fast and is known to generate concise rule sets. The system is a set of association rules and frequent patterns than can be applied to the network traffic to classify it properly. One of the attractive features of this approach is that the generated rule set is easy to understand; hence a security analyst can verify it.

Genetic Algorithms

Genetic algorithms were originally introduced in the field of computational biology. Since then, they have been applied in various fields with promising results. Fairly recently, researchers have tried to integrate these algorithms with IDSs.

C. Fuzzy Logic

Fuzzy logic is derived from fuzzy set theory dealing with reasoning that is approximate rather than precisely deduced from classical predicate logic. It can be thought of as “the application side of fuzzy set theory dealing with well thought out real world expert values for a complex problem”.

D. IMMUNOLOGICAL SYSTEM

Homer and Forrest present an interesting technique based on immunological concepts. They define the set of connections from normal traffic as the “self”, then generate a large number of “non-self” example :connections that are not part of the normal traffic on a machine. These examples are generated using a byte oriented hash and permutation. They can then compare incoming connections using the r-contiguous bits match rule. If a connection matches one of the examples, it is assumed to be in non-self and marked as anomalous.

E. Clustering Techniques

Data clustering is a common technique for statistical data analysis, which is used in many fields, including machine learning, data mining, pattern recognition, image analysis and bio-informatics .Clustering is the classification of similar objects into different groups, or more precisely, the partitioning of a data set into subsets (clusters), so that the data in each subset (ideally) share some common trait – often proximity according to some defined distance measure. Machine learning typically regards data clustering as a form of unsupervised learning. Clustering is useful in intrusion detection as malicious activity should cluster together, separating itself from non-malicious activity.

KDD 99 DATASET

This stands for knowledge data detection. The experiment is carried out on an intrusion detection real data stream which has been used in the Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (KDD) 1999 Cup competition. In total, 41 features have been used in KDD99 dataset and each connection can be categorized into five main classes as one normal class and four main intrusion classes as DOS, U2R, R2L and Probe. . In KDD99 dataset the input data flow contains the details of the network connections, such as protocol type, connection duration, login type etc. Each data sample in KDD99 dataset represents attribute value of a class in the network data flow, and each class is labelled either as normal or as an attack with exactly one specific attack type.

CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a network intrusion detection model using anomaly detection and security of networks through various aspects. The classifier algorithm gives out the algorithmic method of the intrusion detection. Modern intrusion detection applications face complex requirements - they need to be reliable, extensible, easy to manage, and have low maintenance cost. Still, significant challenges exist in design and implementation of production quality IDSs. This paper gives the classifier algorithm model for attack category and ensemble approach for detection

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